

Spousal Approval and Acceptance of Caesarean Section Among Women in Comprehensive Health Centres in Ondo State

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Abstract

There are many scenarios and anecdotal reports in the hospitals, showing maternal mortality due to refusal in consenting to Caesarean section. Therefore, the study examined spousal approval and acceptance of caesarean section among women in comprehensive health centres in Ondo state. The study adopted a descriptive research design of the survey type. The study populations were women of Reproductive age from Comprehensive Health Centres in Ondo State. The total sample size of 400 women was selected but 385 questionnaires were retrieved. Convenient sampling technique was used to select participants for this study. A Self-designed questionnaire was developed by the researcher to collect data from the respondent. The face and content validity of the instrument was ensured by experts of Nurse Education and Tests & Measurement. The Cronbach's Alpha analysis yielded an alpha value of 0.893, thus the instrument was said to be reliable. Data generated from the study were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. From the findings of the study, 145(37.7%) indicated that their husbands and family cannot allow them to undergo CS, while 228(59.2%) accepted that there in-laws will only accept vagina delivery. The percentile rate of acceptance of CS was 41.8%. 59.2% accepted that their In-law will only accept vaginal delivery, the spousal approval on the acceptance of CS was also statistically significant ($P=0.021$). It was recommended among

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others that the right of women in choosing and participating actively in decision making for their mode of delivery should be emphasized in hospitals and broadcasted in mass media as well as promoted to conscious attention.

Keywords: Spousal Approval, Acceptance, Caesarean Section, Women,

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Introduction

Caesarean section (CS) is a life-saving obstetric surgery, it has been defined as delivery of a fetus through a surgical incision into the uterine wall after 28 weeks of gestation, which may be necessitated (sometimes the only feasible option) in high risk pregnancies. These are those with multiple/ large fetuses, breech presentations, obstructed labour, previous caesarean section, Cephalopelvic disproportion, fetal distress, failed induction, previous reconstructive vaginal surgery, abnormal presentation, multiple gestation in excess of three and above. Others include macrosomic baby, fetal abnormality, obstructive pelvic tumors, severe preeclampsia with unfavorable cervix, previous classical CS, major placenta praevia. Other indications are retained second twin, bad obstetrics history, maternal request, prematurity, cord prolapsed, abruption with live fetus as well as in women with transmissible infections such as vulva Herpex, HIV/AIDS prevention of mother to child transmission (PMTCT) (Adewuyi, Auta, Khanal, Samson & Zhao, 2019). Indication for CS can be either Elective or Emergency, in elective a woman have enough time for preparation but for Emergency, decision making must be fast.

In a study by Robinson-Bassey and Uchegbu (2017), CS is seen as a curse on an unfaithful woman and the weak women. It is still believed that these women are lesser than their fellow women, they are believed to be under some sort of punishment by the gods or seen and labeled as the less righteous and faithless woman. Women in less developed countries often think that caesarean section signifies reproductive failure. It is usually bad news for them when told that they will be delivered through Caesarean section. For those that will eventually give their consent, it is done with so much unnecessary delay. This little time between counselling and giving consent for caesarean section may be important in clinical practice for conditions such as foetal distress and antepartum haemorrhage that require emergency Caesarean section. With a positive perception of caesarean section, it is expected that the decision-delivery interval will be reduced (Ezeonu, Ekwedigwe, Isikhuemen, Eliboh, Onoh, Lawani, Ajah & Dimejesi, 2017).

In Nigeria, it has been recorded that women reluctantly accept CS even in the face of obvious clinical indications. The trend of acceptability and the rate of CS have been on the increase in the developed countries in the past two decade, conversely in developing country like Nigeria the rate is sluggish (Owonikoko, Akinola, Adeniji & Bankole, 2015). African has the second highest rate of maternal mortality and the poor utilization of surgical method of delivery is one of the reasons for their high maternal mortality rate (Utuk, Abasiatta, Ekanem, & Nyoyoko, 2018). In 1985, the World Health Organization considers that the best caesarean section rate is between 10-15%. However, the World Health Organization (2015) has since modified this particular recommendation. Stating that the optimum rate is unknown and asserts that the procedure should be done when it is absolutely necessary, in order to reduce maternal mortality rate. Recently, the European Board and College of Gynecology and Obstetrics (EBCOG) in EBCOG survey 2017, it was discovered that only few countries of European Union have less than 20%. In Northern America the increase is rated to be 10% thus the rise is from 22.3% to 32.3%, while in Africa the increase was just 4.5%, from 2.9% to 7.4%. This is due to refusal and underutilization of CS, which is one of the reasons for increment in maternal mortality (Betran, Torloni & Zang 2016).

There are many scenarios and anecdotal reports in the hospitals, showing maternal mortality due to refusal in consenting to Caesarean section. Some disheartening occurrences where there were maternal and fetal mortalities, some of these mothers left behind a young child or children to suffer all in the name of "I must deliver as a Hebrew woman". The

researcher witnessed a scenario; 5th of June 2016, at State Specialist Hospital Akure, Mrs B.B a trader, 42 years old Primigravida refuses emergency CS. The husband believed God cannot be wicked to them and allow his wife to have their first child through CS, also no one has ever had CS in their family. Unfortunately, the baby died in utero and same CS was done to bring out the dead baby because it is transverse lie. These and many other occurrences have prompted the researcher to research on spousal approval and acceptance of caesarean section among women in comprehensive health centres in Ondo state. The study specifically examined:

- i. the influence of Spouse Approval on acceptance of CS among women in comprehensive health centres;
- ii. the acceptance rate of CS among women in comprehensive health centres; and
- iii. the influence of spouse approval on acceptance of CS among women in comprehensive health centres in Ondo state.

Research Questions

The study has the following research questions:

1. What is the influence of Spouse Approval on acceptance of CS among women in comprehensive health centres in Ondo state?
2. What is the acceptance rate of CS among women in comprehensive health centres in Ondo state?

Research Hypothesis

This hypothesis was generated for this study:

1. There is no significant influence of spouse approval on acceptance of CS among women in comprehensive health centres in Ondo state

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive research design of the survey type. The study populations were women of Reproductive age from Comprehensive Health Centres in Ondo State. The total sample size of 400 women was selected but 385 questionnaires were retrieved. Convenient sampling technique was used to select participants for this study.

A Self-designed questionnaire was developed by the researcher to collect data from the respondent. It consisted of three sections; section A sought for demographic characteristics of the respondents while section B consisted of items on spouse approval of CS and section C consisted of items on acceptance of CS. The face and content validity of the instrument was ensured by experts of Nurse Education and Tests & Measurement. After the experts had appraised, they ascertained that the instruments could elicit adequate information to achieve the stated objectives. Reliability of the instrument was carried out through a pilot study among 40 respondents. The Cronbach's Alpha analysis yielded an alpha value of 0.893, thus the instrument was said to be reliable.

Data generated from the study were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage were used to answer the research questions while inferential statistics using regression was used to test the only hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria: Women that are within the reproductive age who indicated an interest to participate.

Exclusion Criteria: Men were excluded from the sample and also mothers who did not want to participate. Menopausal women were also excluded

Results

Research Question 1: What is the influence of Spouse Approval on acceptance of CS among women in comprehensive health centres in Ondo state?

Table 1: Respondents Responses on Spouse Approval as a Factor Affecting CS

S/N	Items	SA N %	A N %	D N %	SD N %
1.	My husband and family cannot allow me to undergo CS	45 11.7	100 26.0	140 36.3	100 26.0
2.	Undergoing CS can make someone's husband remarry.	62 16.1	62 16.1	140 36.4	121 31.4
3.	My in-law will only accept vaginal delivery	128 33.2	100 26.0	62 16.1	95 24.7

Table 1 shows responses to society and spousal approval. The findings revealed that 45(11.7%) of the respondents strongly agree that their husband and family cannot allow them to undergo CS, 100(26.0%) agree, 140(36.3%) disagree, and 100(26.0%) strongly disagree that their husband and family cannot allow them to undergo CS. Further, when asked 62(16.1%) of the respondents strongly agree that undergoing CS can make someone's husband remarry, 62(16.1%) agree, 140(36.4%) disagree, and 121(31.4%) strongly disagree that undergoing CS can make someone's husband remarry. The findings revealed that 128(33.2%) of the respondents strongly agree that their in-law will only accept vaginal delivery, 100(26.0%) agree, 62(16.1%) disagree, and 95(24.7%) strongly disagree that their in-law will only accept vaginal delivery.

Research Question 2: What is the acceptance rate of CS among women in comprehensive health centres in Ondo state?

Table 2: Respondents Acceptance of CS among women in comprehensive health centres in Ondo state

S/N	Items	Yes N %	No N %	Mean	Acceptance Rate
1.	It is the right of the woman to choose her method of delivery	305 79.2	80 20.8	0.79	41.8%
2.	I will have a CS based on the Doctor advice	161 41.8	224 58.2	0.42	
3.	I had babies already through vaginal delivery, I don't need CS	322 83.6	63 16.4	0.84	

Table 2 shows respondent acceptance of CS responses. The findings revealed that 305(79.2%) of the respondents indicated Yes that it is the right of the woman to choose her method of delivery, while 80(20.8%) indicated No. Further, 161(41.8%) of the respondents indicated that they will have a CS based on Doctors' advice, 224(58.2%) indicated that they will not have a CS based on Doctors' advice. The findings further revealed the number of respondents that indicated Yes to the statement "I had already babies through vaginal delivery, I don't need CS" were 322(83.6%), those that indicated No was 63(16.4%). The acceptance rate was 41.8%

Testing of Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant influence of Spouse Approval on acceptance of CS among women in comprehensive health centres in Ondo state.

Table 3: Result of Binary Logistic Regression Between spouse approval and Acceptance of CS

Constant	Chi-Square	Model Summary Cox & Snell R ² Nagelkerke R ²	Predicted (Percentage)	B Exp(B)	Significance
-.330	-21.329	0.055 0.073	59.2	0.114 0.892	P = 0.031 P < 0.05

Table 4: Model summary of Linear Regression between Acceptance of CS and spouse approval

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.467 ^a	.218	.212	.415
a. Predictors: (Constant) spousal approval				
b. Dependent Variable: acceptance of CS				

Table 5: ANOVA analysis between Acceptance of CS and spouse approval

ANOVA ^a						
	Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	18.348	3	6.116	35.459	.000 ^b
	Residual	65.714	381	.172		
	Total	84.062	384			
a. Dependent Variable: acceptance of CS						
b. Predictors: (Constant) spouse approval						

Table 6: Coefficient of Regression between Acceptance of CS and spouse approval

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.216	.057		21.438	.000
	My husband and family cannot allow me to undergo CS	-.141	.031	-.300	-4.597	.000
	Undergoing CS can make someone's husband remarry	-.061	.026	-.134	-2.322	.021

My in-law will only accept Vaginal delivery	-0.044	.030	-0.099	-1.454	.147
Dependent Variable: acceptance of CS					

From Table 4.12 (a-c), the result of the linear regression analysis between spouse/significant others decision and acceptance of CS showed that there is significant relationship between spouse/significant others' decision and acceptance of CS; $F(3, 381) = 35.459, p = 0.000$. Regression analysis showed that spousal decisions influence acceptance of CS ($p = 0.000, 0.021$). Thus, the null hypothesis which says there is no significant influence between spouse/significant others' decisions and acceptance of CS is rejected.

Discussion

The findings revealed that 128(33.2%) of the respondents strongly agree that their in-law will only accept vaginal delivery and another 100(26.0) agree. This finding is in line with Ugwu and De-Kok (2015) study that there are restrictive gender roles in decision making about CS between women and their spouses and mothers-in-law roles in decision making. A woman who delivered by CS is seen by the husband and the in-law as an incompetent woman and the husband will need to marry another woman, who is believed to be competent because she can deliver per vagina. This finding were also confirmed by the 62(16.1%) and 62(16.1%) of the respondents in this study that strongly agree and agree respectively that undergoing CS can make someone's husband remarry.

The work of Anyasor and Adetuga (2017), is in line with this as 39 (37.9%) respondents believed that having a caesarean section can make someone's husband to remarry, while the study of Owonikoko, Akinola, Adeniji and Bankole (2015), confirmed this trend of negative reactions from relatives. 45(11.7%) and 100(26.0%) of the respondents strongly agree and agree respectively that their husbands and family cannot allow them to undergo CS. This is in line with Amiegheme, Adeyemo and Onasoga (2016), where 82% objected CS due to family preference of vaginal delivery. This may not be entirely surprising as the majority of decisions are often left for the men who are believed to be the head of the family.

Interestingly, Ezeonu, et al., (2017) affirm that a good number of women (66.5%) believe their husbands should be the one to give consent for caesarean section. This is not entirely surprising in this setting as the majority of decisions are often left for the men who are believed to be the head of the family. Anyasor and Adetuga's (2017) study findings supported this with the finding that husband's preference for vaginal delivery seems to be a major factor that hinders the acceptance of Caesarean section as majority 73 (70.9%) of the respondents agreed to it. This was also supported by Ezeome, Ezugworie and Udealor (2018), where 164 (82%) of women will agree to a Caesarean delivery if their husbands consent despite their own personal disapproval because he is the head of the family, About a tenth of the women in the study are of the view that women should take the decision solely on her own. These points out that psychological support and financial need may be responsible for this outcome.

The findings of this study shows that 41.8% of the participants will accept a CS if the doctor advised it. This figure amount to 161 of the respondents, this acceptance rate is lower to other acceptability rates that have been recorded in recent studies. This is pointing to an underutilization of this vital procedure when compared to the large burden of obstetric

morbidity requiring resolution by Caesarean section. Specifically, the study is in tandem with earlier reports of Faremi, Ibitoye, Olatubi, Koledoye & Ogbeye (2014), where 42.9% said they will agree if given the option of Caesarean section for their next delivery, also Olofinbiyi, Olofinbiyi, Aduloju, Atiba, Olaogun & Ogundare (2015), showed that majority (69.2%) would accept a repeat Caesarean section. There is also a higher acceptance rate observed by Prah, Kudom, Lasim & Abu (2017) and Anyasor and Adetuga (2017), where majority 94.6% and 92.2% of the pregnant women said they would agree to Caesarean birth if indicated for them respectively. It is however sad that some women will insist on vaginal delivery even when contra-indicated and not safe for their health and that of the unborn baby even despite repeated counselling on the potential danger of such action.

The study revealed that there is significant influence of spouse approval on the acceptance of CS based on women of reproductive age. These findings did not differ from the findings of Ugwu and De-Kok, (2015) that the husband makes the decision for the wife, and Ezeonu et al. (2017) posits that a good number of women believe their husbands should be the one to give consent for Caesarean section. Anyasor and Adetuga (2017) said husband's preference for vaginal delivery seems to be a major factor that hinders the acceptance of Caesarean section.

Conclusion

The study concludes that there are concerns about the high cost of CS, refusal of husband and in-laws in consenting to CS is also a militating factor faced by these women even at the detriment of their own lives. The rate of CS acceptance of CS in the study was 41.8%. This confirms that there is an underutilization of this vital procedure when compared to the large burden of obstetric morbidity requiring resolution by Caesarean section. It was also concluded that there is influence of spouse approval on the acceptance of CS based on women of reproductive age.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The right of women in choosing and participating actively in decision making for their mode of delivery should be emphasized in hospitals and broadcasted in mass media as well as promoted to conscious attention. Empowering women to take decisions that will be to the best of their interest is a key.
2. Since husbands and in-laws were mentioned as a determinant in CS acceptance, men should be encouraged to participate in the antenatal care of their wives as well as seminars that involve maternal health.
3. Nurses and midwives should explain carefully the benefits and the possible risks/complications associated with CS to clients at the antenatal clinic. All available birthing methods should also be explained giving the merit and demerits to the clients during antenatal clinic sessions.

Implication of Findings to Nurses

There are implications of this finding to nursing practice in Nigeria and beyond. There is a need for nurses to be more sensitive and aware of the patient's challenges. Also, frequent empathic conversations with reproductive women on CS will bridge the knowledge gap among them. Nurses and midwives should explain carefully the benefits and the possible risk and complications associated with CS to clients at the antenatal clinic. All available birthing methods should also be explained giving the merit and demerits to the clients during

antenatal clinic sessions. This means nurses need to move away from the traditional way of top-bottom thinking to horizontal and participatory thinking. This also embraces the need of applying a research-based understanding of CS in nursing and midwifery education by incorporating knowledge on the need to teach expectant mothers on birthing methods, their effects, and the need to accept the best method for them. This knowledge can be extended to manners that are culturally effective and congruent in Nigeria or African setting.

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